

SULPHINATION. PART II. SULPHINATION OF SOME 7-HYDROXYCOUMARIN DERIVATIVES

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Action of thionyl chloride on 4-methyl-6-propyl-7-hydroxycoumarin, 4-methyl-7-hydroxy-8-ethylcoumarin and methyl 4-methyl-7-hydroxy coumarin-6-carboxylate in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride has now been studied. The first two coumarin derivatives react smoothly to give rise to respective sulphinic acids, while no reaction takes place on the last.

In continuation of our previous communication (this *Journal*, 1958, 35, 251) the action of thionyl chloride on 4-methyl-6-propyl-7-hydroxycoumarin and 4-methyl-7-hydroxy-8-ethylcoumarin in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride has been studied. Both the coumarins react smoothly, furnishing 4-methyl-6-propyl-7-hydroxycoumarin-8-sulphinic acid (I) and 4-methyl-7-hydroxy-8-ethylcoumarin-6-sulphinic acid (II) respectively, the sulphinic acid group entering into the position-8 in the former and the position-6 in the latter (the only free positions *ortho* to hydroxyl group in the respective coumarin derivatives). Both the sulphinic acids exhibit characteristic coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride, establishing the fact that $-SO_2H$ group is in position *ortho* to OH group.

The sulphonation of these coumarin derivatives with chlorosulphonic acid furnished the respective sulphonic acids which were found identical with those obtained by oxidation of the sulphinic acids (I) and (II), respectively, as judged by the mixed m.p. of the *s*-benzylisothiurea derivatives.

Attempts to sulphonate methyl 4-methyl-7-hydroxycoumarin-6-carboxylate with thionyl chloride met with failures.

EXPERIMENTAL

4-Methyl-6-propyl-7-hydroxycoumarin-8-sulphinic Acid (I)

Thionyl chloride (2.4 g.) was gradually added to an intimate mixture of powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride (4.2 g.) and 4-methyl-6-propyl-7-hydroxycoumarin (2 g.), cooled in ice and protected from moisture. It was left overnight at room temperature, and then decomposed by adding crushed ice and HCl. The resulting solution was kept in the refrigerator after scratching the walls of the container. The impure solid that separated after drying in vacuum was triturated with ammonia and then diluted with water. The insoluble residue contained, besides other byproducts, some amount of the ammonium salt of the sulphinic acid. The acid was recovered from it by extracting the residue with hot water and acidifying the extract.

The original ammoniacal filtrate was just acidified with HCl, when a dirty precipitate separated, which was filtered. To the clear filtrate more HCl was added, when sulphinic acid slowly separated. The dirty precipitate contained a little

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amount of sulphinic acid as its ammonium salt. It was recovered by extracting it with hot water and acidifying the extract. The sulphinic acid was collected, washed well and dried in vacuum, m.p. 160-65° (decomp.), yield 1.5 g. It was crystallised from alcohol as white needles, m.p. 177-78° (decomp.). (Found: S, 11.79. $C_{13}H_{14}O_3S$ requires S, 11.34%).

It developed a blue coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride, and no fluorescence with alkali.

The *ammonium salt* was prepared by passing dry ammonia gas in an ice-cooled alcoholic solution of the sulphinic acid. It crystallised from alcohol (with few drops of water) in shining square plates, m.p. 214-15° (decomp.). (Found: N, 4.69. $C_{13}H_{17}O_3NS$ requires N, 4.68%).

s-Benzylisothiourea derivative was prepared by adding an aqueous solution of *s*-benzylisothiourea hydrochloride to the aqueous solution of the potassium salt. (Potassium salt was obtained by adding alcoholic potash dropwise to the alcoholic solution of sulphinic acid till yellow tinge appeared in the solution). It crystallised from alcohol in tiny needles, m.p. 155-56° (decomp.). (Found: N, 6.56. $C_{21}H_{24}O_3N_2S_2$ requires N, 6.25%).

4-Methyl-6-propyl-7-hydroxycoumarin-8-sulphonic Acid: (i) Oxidation of Sulphinic Acid (I).—Hydrogen peroxide (3 c.c. of 100 vol., diluted to 10 c.c.) was added to the potassium salt of the sulphinic acid (0.5 g.), suspended in water. It was left overnight at room temperature and then heated on a water-bath for half an hour and then cooled. The potassium salt of sulphonic acid slowly separated. It crystallised from water in shining needles.

s-Benzylisothiourea derivative, prepared from the above potassium salt, crystallised from dilute alcohol in thin needles, m.p. 174-75°. (Found: N, 6.18. $C_{21}H_{24}O_3N_2S_2$ requires N, 6.04%).

(ii) Sulphonation with Chlorosulphonic Acid.—Chlorosulphonic acid (1.3 c.c.) was gradually added to 4-methyl-6-propyl-7-hydroxycoumarin (1 g.) and the mixture (protected from moisture) was heated on a water-bath for 2½ hours, then cooled and poured over crushed ice. The solution was filtered and boiled to drive off hydrogen chloride. It was concentrated to a small bulk and then added to a small quantity of saturated solution of common salt, when sodium salt of sulphonic acid slowly separated. It was filtered, washed and dried.

s-Benzylisothiourea derivative, prepared from the above sodium salt, crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. and mixed m.p. with previous specimen, 174-75°.

4-Methyl-6-propyl-7-hydroxycoumarin-8-ethylsulphone.—A solution of potassium salt of sulphinic acid (I, 0.7 g.) in a mixture of alcohol (4 c.c.) and water (3 c.c.) was refluxed with ethyl iodide (10.8 c.c.) for 18 hours. The reaction mixture was filtered hot. From the filtrate the sulphone slowly crystallised out. The solid was washed with thiosulphate solution to remove iodine and then with water. It was crystallised from alcohol in white shining plates, m.p. 145-47°. (Found: S, 10.42. $C_{17}H_{18}O_3S$ requires S, 10.32%).

4-Methyl-7-hydroxy-8-ethylcoumarin-6-sulphinic Acid (II)

Thionyl chloride (1.5 c.c.) was gradually added to an intimate mixture of powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride (4.4 g.) and 4-methyl-7-hydroxy-8-ethylcoumarin (2 g.) (Limaye and Ghate, *Rasayanam*, 1939, 6, 171) and the reaction was allowed to proceed in the same way as before, and was worked up similarly.

The residue obtained after triturating the crude solid with ammonia was found to be mainly the unchanged coumarin. The solution was just acidified with HCl and the mud-like precipitate separating was removed, and to the clear filtrate more HCl was added, scratched and left in the refrigerator. The sulphinic acid, which slowly separated, was collected, washed with water and dried in vacuum, m.p. 150° (decomp.), yield 1-1.2 g. It was crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 155° (decomp.). (Found: S, 11.97. $C_{12}H_{12}O_5S$ requires S, 11.94%).

It developed a violet coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride, and no fluorescence with alkali.

The *ammonium salt* was prepared and crystallised as before in shining needles, m.p. 204-205° (decomp.). (Found: S, 4.98. $C_{12}H_{12}O_5NS$ requires S, 4.91%).

s-Benzylisothiouréa derivative, prepared as usual from the sulphinic acid (by first preparing the neutral solution of sodium salt of sulphinic acid), was crystallised from dilute alcohol in glistening needles, m.p. 190-92° (decomp.). (Found: N, 6.80. $C_{10}H_{12}O_5N_2S_2$ requires N, 6.45%).

4-Methyl-7-hydroxy-8-ethylcoumarin-6-sulphonic Acid: (i) *Oxidation of Sulphinic Acid* (II).—Hydrogen peroxide (3 c.c. of 100 vol. and 7 c.c. of water) was added to the solution of the sulphinic acid (0.5 g.) in sodium bicarbonate solution (5 c.c.). The reaction mixture was left aside at room temperature for some time and then heated on a water-bath for about an hour. It was cooled, just acidified with HCl and then filtered from any impurities. The solution was concentrated to a small bulk and poured in a saturated solution of common salt and cooled. The sodium salt of sulphonic acid slowly separated as a crystalline solid.

s-Benzylisothiouréa derivative, prepared from the sodium salt, was crystallised from dilute alcohol in shining plates, m.p. 125-27°. (Found: N, 6.56. $C_{20}H_{22}O_6N_2S_2$ requires N, 6.22%).

(ii) *Sulphonation with Chlorosulphonic Acid*.—Chlorosulphonic acid (0.8 c.c.) was gradually added to 4-methyl-7-hydroxy-8-ethylcoumarin (1 g.) and the mixture, protected from moisture, was heated on a water-bath for 2 hours. It was cooled, well mixed with crushed ice and the resulting solution was filtered. The filtrate was boiled to drive off HCl, concentrated to a small bulk and added to a saturated solution of common salt and then kept in the refrigerator, when a white sodium salt separated. It was filtered, washed with alcohol and dried.

s-Benzylisothiouréa derivative, prepared from the sodium salt, was crystallised from alcohol in shining plates, m.p. and mixed m.p. with the previous specimen, 125-27°.

4-Methyl-7-hydroxy-8-ethylcoumarin-6-ethylsulphone.—A solution of ammonium salt of the sulphinic acid (II, 0.5 g.) in a mixture of alcohol (8 c.c.) and water (4 c.c.) was refluxed with ethyl iodide (0.8 c.c.) for 18 hours. The solution was filtered hot, and concentrated. The crystalline solid separating was washed with a thiosulphate solution to remove iodine and then with a little alcohol. It was crystallised from alcohol in white needles, m.p. 162-63°. (Found: S, 10.4. $C_{14}H_{18}O_3S$ requires S, 10.8 %).

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